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Factors Affecting Teaching Practice Assessment in Teachers' Colleges in Zimbabwe and their Implications on Professional Development of Student Teachers

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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

The study sought to find out factors affecting teaching practice assessment by lecturers at Morgan Teachers' College. The study also sought to find out the impact of assessment on the professional development of student teachers. The case study design was employed and the questionnaire was used to collect data. A sample of forty- three (43) lecturers out of a population of 90 lecturers participated in this research. The lecturers who participated in this study were preferred because they were involved in the assessment of teaching during teaching practice but did not have experience of teaching in primary school. The SPSS programme was used to analyse the data and produce the frequencies. The study found out that assessments of teaching practice by lecturers were not reliable. Lecturers preferred to assess trainee teachers teach in a subject area in which they had solid content knowledge. The conclusion is that student teachers do not get adequate professional preparation and grounding teaching practice when assessed by lecturers who were non-specialists. The study recommends that college lecturers should be oriented in assessing teaching practice upon appointment. Lecturers should assess students teaching a subject area in which they are knowledgeable in to avoid subjective assessment of teaching practice.

Keywords: Assessment, Teaching Practice, Professional Development.

INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

In Zimbabwe students in primary teachers colleges go on teaching practice for five terms and do theory for four terms known as the 2-5-2 model of teaching practice (Maposa and Ndamba, 2012). The purpose of this study is to investigate the effectiveness of supervision by lecturers in the professional development of student teachers. Teaching practice, sometimes called school placement constitutes an important part of the teacher- training programme. It is probably the most challenging and exciting phase of initial teacher training as well as the first real opportunity to test and develop the students' teaching skills. At Morgan Teachers' College, student teachers are attached to schools under a mentor for practical teaching in real classroom situations for five terms, starting with the third term of the first year.

Teaching practice has a dual role. Whilst students are developing and testing their teaching skills, they are also being assessed. It is therefore important that they are given the appropriate support and the opportunity to make a good start. Gipps (1994) describes assessment as a systematic process that begins with goals and ends with a judgment concerning the extent to which set goals have been achieved. Lecturers visit schools to assess student performances and award a mark. These assessments are made while students teach any subject in the primary school curriculum. Though lecturers are specialists in one or two academic areas, they are expected to assess teaching in all the subjects of the primary school curriculum.

The teaching practice assessment instrument used by the institution has guidelines on what to look for in a lesson. Uhlenbeck et al. (2002) identified performance assessment as commonly used in assessment of student teachers; its main challenge is its validity and reliability. Stones and Morris (1981) raise the issue of reliability and

validity of the assessment instrument. They identified challenges facing teaching practice assessment. These include

- The teaching mark lacks validity and reliability
- Assessment by grading lacks practical value
- It hinders the student realisation of objectives of teaching practice and can impair the student tutor relationship.

With its challenges the performance-based assessment is widely used in Zimbabwean teachers training colleges. The question that arises is whether all lecturers can apply it effectively and consistently when assessing different subjects. To this effect, Brown and Brown (1990) observes that there are inconsistencies between different assessors who assess the same student and Shumbayaonda (1991) raises the issue of lack of training on the part of lecturers on how to assess practical teaching are weakness facing teaching practice. This means there is need for adequate and appropriate orientation and training of lecturers on teaching practice assessment so as to satisfy the pedagogical demands of the subjects offered at primary school and minimize inconsistencies.

According to Shumbayaonda (1991), it should be noted that the effectiveness of teaching practice assessment is influenced by experience and knowledge base of the lecturers on practical teaching and subject content. Hence experience and expertise play an important role in ensuring effective teaching practice assessment. One of the assumptions of this research is that teaching practice assessment is fraught with inconsistencies and subjectivity. Hence several authors such as Rowntree (1977), Harlen (1987), Grounlund (1995), Sax (1989), and Makoni (2000) emphasize the need to ensure consistency as well as validity and reliability of teaching practice assessment. This can be achieved by well oriented or trained lecturers in assessment of practical teaching. It is hoped that findings of this study will contribute towards effective assessment of teaching practice and relevant staff development programmes for lecturers. The findings will also assist in reducing subjectivity in teaching practice assessment.

Statement of the problem

Teaching practice assessment in Zimbabwe is fraught with inconsistencies and lack of reliability and validity. Most lecturers do not have basic training in assessing practical teaching. Hence this research sought to find out factors affecting teaching practice assessment by college lecturers and how these factors impact on professional development of student teachers.

Research Objectives

- To identify factors affecting teaching practice assessment in teachers colleges
- To determine the content knowledge gap on teaching practice assessment which exist among lecturers
- To investigate on how teaching practice assessment can be improved

Research Questions

Therefore the study seeks to find answers to the following research questions:

- What factors militate against effective assessment of teaching practice?
- What content knowledge gap on teaching practice assessment exists among lecturers?
- How can teaching practice assessment be improved?

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

What is Assessment?

According to Brown and Brown (1990) assessment consists essentially of lecturers taking a sample of what students do, making inferences and estimating the worth of their actions. It is imperative that lecturers be accountable of their actions in assessment of student teachers during teaching practice.

Purposes of Assessment

Different stakeholders have various expectations of assessment. In teaching practice assessment students want to know what is expected of them, how they will be judged and how they are progressing. They also want recognition of their achievements. Lecturers assess whether students have mastered key concepts and skills, in teaching. Colleges want to know whether their graduates are achieving high standards, set by the institution or government (Luckett and Sutherland cited in Makoni, 2000), hence producing teachers who are skilled and competent performers (Avalos, 1990). This can only be achieved through dialogue between students and assessors as observed by Yost et al. (2000) who encouraged more dialogue, writing and action research to assist student teachers in reining deeply about their practice. The question is, how much advice or content can a specialist or worse still a non-specialist lecturer discuss with or writes for a student during a 30 minute or 1 hour lesson.

Forms of Assessment

There are various forms of assessment, which are based on purposes such as diagnostic assessment, formative assessment, summative assessment and quality assurance (Rowntree, 1977; Harlen 1987; Gronlund, 1995; Sax, 1989; Luckett and Sutherland, 2000). Teaching practice assessment is both formative and summative (Luckett and Sutherland, 2000). It is important to note that through summative assessment supervisors exert the greatest power over students hence it is vital that they exercise this power responsibly and accountably.

Different stakeholders have varied expectations out of assessment. For example, educational institutions want to know whether their graduates are achieving high standards, set by the institution (Luckett and Sutherland, 2000; Harlen (1987). Students want to know what is expected of them, how they are judged and how they are progressing and also want recognition of their achievements. During teaching practice assessment lecturers want to know whether the students have mastered key concepts and skills necessary in teaching.

Assessment of Teaching Practice

An assessment form guides assessment of teaching practice. The form has outlined items of what to look for in a lesson. This could be more of criterion-referenced assessment where the performance is judged against pre-specified criteria or standards. Here the student's performance is compared to that of his or her peers (Brown and Brown 1990). An institution can use assessment carried out by lecturers to determine failure or passing of teaching practice. It is therefore important to choose the most appropriate method to suit the purpose of assessment.

Research has shown that there are great inconsistencies between different assessors assessing the same work and there is need to minimize these inconsistencies in teaching practice assessment (Brown, 1997). Assessment is influenced by approaches to assessment such as the traditional approach where the lecturers are usually considered to be the only legitimate assessors and integrated assessment or computer –based assessment. Lecturers are the key assessors of students' performance during teaching practice. Their assessment relies heavily on their professional judgment. This raises the question of objectivity since lecturers assess a student who would be teaching any of the subjects in some of the curriculum, of which they may not be, specialists in.

According to Lockett and Sutherland (2000), in assessment, the issues of objectivity and subjectivity will always arise among scholars. There is need to acknowledge that different assessors interpret student performances using different standards. The issues of inconsistencies can be minimized by double grading or cross grading to improve reliability. However assessors need to make reliable and valid qualitative and quantitative judgment when assessing teaching practice (Luckett and Sutherland, 2000).

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The case study method was used in this study. The case study was preferred because it gave a more focused study of Morgan Teachers College.

Population and Sample

The population is made up of 90 lecturers. Forty-three lecturers at Morgan Teachers College were purposively selected on the basis of willingness to respond to a questionnaire out of a population of 90 lecturers. These lecturers

were preferred because they were willing to provide the relevant data on teaching practice assessment. Morgan Teachers College was preferred because it is an Open and Distance Learning (ODL) institution. The purposive sampling technique was used to select the respondents.

Data Collection and Analysis

A questionnaire was used to collect data. Lecturers responded to closed- and open-ended questions. The questionnaire was preferred because it enabled lecturers to give their own experience on teaching practice. These lecturers had been involved in teaching practice assessment in the distance education mode of training of teachers. The SPSS programme was used to analyse the data and produce frequencies.

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Data Presentation and Discussion

Table 1: Sex Composition

	N	Percentage
Male	22	51.2%
Female	21	48.8%
Total	43	100%

N=43

The distribution of lecturers who participated in this research shows that 51.2% were males and 48.8% were females. As such the results of this study were not influenced by gender imbalances.

Table 2: Work Experience

	N	Percentage
Below 5 years	29	67.4%
6 – 10 years	11	25.6%
Above 10 years	3	7%
Total	43	100%

N=43

The majority of the lecturers (67.4%) had less than 5 years of lecturing experience. The years of experience have a bearing on the results of the study since it shows that the majority of the lecturers had little experience in supervision of teaching experience as such they needed more guidance and staff development.

Table 3: Distribution of lecturers in Area of Specialisation

Subject	N	Percentage
Social studies	11	25.6%
Theory of Education	16	37.2%
Mathematics	4	9.3%
Sciences	5	11.6%
Practicals	4	9.3%
Total	43	100%

Table 3 shows that most of the lecturers who participated in this research specialised in Theory of education (37%), and Social studies (25.6%). Only a few were specialized in Mathematics, Science and practical subject. In Teacher Education, Theory of education lays a foundational theoretical framework for effective teaching. As such the participation of more lecturers from the Theory of Education Department ensured that the researchers gather relevant data as it relates to teacher preparation.

Table 4: Qualifications of lecturers

Qualification	N	Percentage
Undergraduate Degree	19	44.2%
Masters Degree	24	55.8%
Total	43	100%

N=43

Most of the lecturers (55.8%) who participated in this study had a masters' degree and only 44.2% had undergraduate degree qualifications. With more lecturers having a post-graduate qualification the assumption is that students will be effectively trained and guided well in their professional development by these experts.

Table 5: Primary School Subjects Lecturers' Ability to Assess Effectively

	N	Percentage
Able to assess all subjects	15	34.9%
Not Able to assess all subjects	28	65.1%
Total	43	100%

N=43

Most lecturers (65.1%) could not assess students teach all the subjects of the primary school curriculum. However, 34.9% claimed that they could assess students teach in all the subjects in the primary school curriculum. It seems most lecturers were not in a position to assess students teaching any subject in the primary school but would prefer to assess students teach certain subjects in which they were more comfortable.

Table 6: Level of Competency in Assessment of Teaching Practice

Subjects	Not competent			Just competent			Very competent		
	N	R	%	N	R	%	N	R	%
Mathematics	31	1	72.1%	10	6	23.3%	2	7	4.7%
English	29	2	67.4%	12	4	27.9%	2	7	4.7%
Shona	29	2	67.4%	11	5	25.6%	3	6	7%
Social Studies	28	3	65.1%	8	7	18.6%	7	4	16.3%
Environmental Studies	27	4	62.8%	13	3	30.2%	3	6	7%
AIDS Education	21	5	48.9%	16	2	37.1%	6	5	14%
Art	20	6	46.5%	12	4	28%	11	3	25.5%

			%						
Home Economics	19	7	44.2%	13	3	30.2%	11	3	25.6%
Physical Education	18	8	41.9%	12	4	27.9%	13	2	30.2%
Religious and Moral Education	17	9	39.5%	20	1	46.5%	6	5	14%
Music	14	10	32.5%	11	5	25.6%	18	1	41.9%

N=43 R= Rank

Asked to indicate the lecturers' own level of competency in the assessment of practical teaching, most lecturers revealed that they were not competent to assess Mathematics (72.1%), English (67.4%), Shona (67.4%), Social Studies (65.1%), Environmental Studies (62.8%), Home Economics (44.2%), AIDS Education (48.9%) and Art (46.5%). Most lecturers though indicated that they were very competent in assessing music yet this is a specialist area and colleges have found that it is difficult to get highly qualified lecturers in this area.

Table 7: Orientation of Lecturers on Appointment

Little extent		Not sure		To a great extent	
N	%	N	%	N	%
11	26%	11	26%	21	48.8%

In trying to determine the extent to which lecturers have been oriented when they were appointed, almost half of the lecturers (48.8%) indicated that they were oriented to a great extent, 26% were oriented to a little extent and another 26% were not sure if they were adequately oriented.

Table 8: Factors Contributing to Failure to Assess Effectively

Statement	Agree			Not sure			Disagree		
	N	R	%	N	R	%	N	R	%
Lack of relevant Past teaching experience	30	1	69.8%	6	5	14%	7	4	16.3%
Inadequate time for assessment	29	2	67.5%	5	4	11.6%	9	3	20.9%
Lack of specialist pedagogical knowledge	28	3	65.1%	5	4	11.6%	10	2	23.3%
Lack of content in subject area	26	4	60.5%	5	4	11.7%	12	1	27.9%
Lack of supervisory skills	25	5	60.5%	8	2	16.3%	10	2	23.3%
Limitation in scope of assessment instrument	23	6	53.5%	11	1	25.6%	9	3	21.9%

N=43 R=Ranking

The majority of the lecturers concurred, that the following factors contributed to failure to effectively assess students practical teaching; these included past teaching experience, area of specialization, lack of content in subject area and inadequate time for assessment, limitation in the scope of the assessment instruments. The factors need to be ranked when presented as per the findings.

Table 9: Factors That Can Assist In Improving the Assessment of Teaching Practice

Statement	Agree			Not sure			Disagree		
	N	R	%	N	R	%	N	R	%
Lecturers need adequate orientation	34	1	80.1%	5	2	11.6%	4	4	9.3%
Lecturers need to be continuously staff developed	32	2	74.4%	5	2	11.6%	6	3	14%
Lecturers should only assess subjects of specialisation	22	3	60.2%	6	1	14%	15	2	34.8%
Pair or team assessment	22	3	60.2%	5	2	11.6%	16	1	37.2%

N=43 R= Rank

The majority of lecturers (74.4%) indicated that assessment can be more effective and can be improved through staff development, adequate orientation (80.1%), team/pair assessment (60.2) and ensuring lecturers assess subjects in which they are specialists (60.2%).

DISCUSSION

Most lecturers were not effective in assessing students teach subject areas in which they were not specialists. Lecturers also indicated that they were not competent in assessing effectively the following subjects; English, Mathematics, Shona, Environmental Studies, Art, Physical Education, Home Economics, and AIDS education. Lecturers were not able to assess students teach most of the subjects of the primary school curriculum. Lecturers were not equipped to assessing most subjects of the primary school curriculum. The conclusion is that lecturers are not assisting students in their professional development and assessment of practical teaching is not reliable.

The lecturers identified the following factors as contributing to their competency in assessing teaching practice. These included lack of past teaching experience, lack of pedagogical knowledge, the limited scope of the assessment instrument, lack of subject content, and inadequate time for effective assessment during teaching practice. These results concur with the observations made by Shumbayaonda (1991) that the lecturers lacked content and training in teaching practice assessment. The lecturers found the assessment instrument as limited in scope and they were not aware of the pedagogical knowledge needed to assist students relevant to the primary school curriculum.

To improve teaching practice assessment the lecturers suggested the following strategies as useful; these included lecturers assessing their areas of specialization only, staff development of lecturers in the area of teaching practice assessment, proper orientation of lecturers upon appointment as college lecturers and the need to ensure that there is team or pair assessment approach used in teaching practice assessment in teachers colleges.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Lecturers in teachers colleges should only assess students teaching in a subject area in which they have adequate content knowledge as well as the pedagogical know-how.
- Lecturers should be thoroughly oriented in the area of teaching practice assessment upon appointment to the position of lecturer.
- Lectures should be trained in the area of teaching practice assessment and need to be staff developed from time to time.
- Recruitment of lecturers to lecture in primary training teachers' colleges should consider relevant past experience to primary school teaching so that these lecturers can assist with hands on approaches to primary school teaching.
- Teachers' Colleges need to introduce team or pair assessment during teaching practice assessment to improve on effectiveness.
- The teaching practice assessment instrument needs to be improved to enhance its objectivity and lecturers should spend more time with the students during classroom observation and teaching practice assessment.

CONCLUSION

The researchers concluded that student teachers did not get adequate grounding and preparation as professionals to teach effectively with confidence in the primary upon completion of the programme. Lecturers were not oriented to assess teaching practice upon appointment and they lack content knowledge to objectively assess student teachers during teaching practice.

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